

Modelling Individual Genetic Distances from Self Reported Welsh Ancestry

Sevval Bahceci - April 2026

SUMMARY

Human populations differ slightly in their genetic variation due to shared ancestry among the majority of the population. These differences can be measured by using statistics as FST. In this project I conducted in Wales, I used published FST values from British populations to calculate the genetic difference between 5 Welsh participants. The goal was to explore whether ancestry labels can be used to approximate genetic similarity in a simplified model.

The Fixation Index is a measure of genetic differences due to genetic structure. FST is directly related to the variance in allele frequency among populations and, conversely, to the degree of resemblance among individuals within populations. The greater the genetic distance between populations, it indicates higher allele variance and less inbreeding in groups. This genetic distance value is known as FST value, calculating the reduction in heterozygosity within sub populations compared to the total population. Ranging from 1 to 0, a value of 0 indicates no difference, while 1 indicates complete separation.

METHODS

One of the primary data sources for this project is the large scale British populations genetic research "*The Fine-Scale Genetic Structure of the British Population (Leslie et al., 2015)*" This study provides an insight of the genetic variation across the United Kingdom, offering a large scale data base of FST values and visual interpretation.

Five elderly Welsh participants were interviewed to gather qualitative information about their family backgrounds and their self reported heritage. Each participant provided a brief data about their background, including their place of origin. All participants are anonymized and assigned numbers from 1-5 to maintain their privacy.

Participant 1: Born near Pontypridd; both parents from Pontypridd, maternal grandparents from Hereford, paternal grandparents from Wales (not specified).

Participant 2: Born in Cardiff; both parents from Cardiff, grandparents from Hampshire

Participant 3: Born in England; grandparents and mom from near Port Talbot, grandparents grandparents from around Bridgend, Swansea

Participant 4: Born in Cardiff; father from Grangetown, mother from Barry, grandparents from Devon and Swansea. Their surname originates from Cumberland.

Participant 5: Born in Cardiff; Grandparents from Forest of Dean, near the England-Wales border.

Each participant was then mapped to the closest available reference region in the Leslie et al. dataset (e.g., Herefordshire, Hampshire, Devon, Cumberland, Forest of Dean). Distances

between participants were calculated by comparing the FST values of their assigned regions.

Because FST itself is not a distance metric, I transformed it using,

$$\rho(i,j) = \sqrt{FST(i,j)}$$

RESULTS

The distance calculation results shown in *Figure 1*, interpreted very close distance between the participants resulting from historically high rates of internal migration and genetic mixing. Due to published data most calculations were able to be done between Participant 3 and Participant 4.

Participant 4 (LAN)	Participant 5 (FOD)	= 0.0316227766
Participant 3 (SPE)	Participant 5 (FOD)	= 0.0316227766
Participant 3 (SPE)	Participant 5 (GLO)	= 0.0316227766
Participant 3 (SPE)	Participant 4 (CUM)	= 0.0316227766
Participant 3 (SPE)	Participant 4 (DEV)	= 0.0316227766
Participant 3 (SPE)	Participant 2 (HAM)	= 0.0316227766
Participant 3 (SPE)	Participant 4 (LAN)	= 0.0316227766
Participant 3 (SPE)	Participant 1 (HER)	= 0.0316227766

Figure 1

All pairwise distances between participants were identical, with a ρ value of 0.0316. This reflects the fact that the reference regions associated with the participants (Herefordshire, Hampshire, Devon, Cumberland, Forest of Dean, and South Pembrokeshire) show extremely low FST differentiation in the Leslie et al. dataset. As a result, every participant pair produced the same transformed distance value. This indicates that, at the population level, these regions are genetically very similar.

DISCUSSION

A small value like this suggests that the allele frequencies within the population are similar, reflecting the fact that European populations are genetically corresponding. In this project people from different regions didn't suggest more diversity as the distance they had between each other remained unchanged. FST differences exist because of mutations, geographic isolation and limited gene flow. These factors result in different populations to have variant Haplogroup frequencies, contributing directly to observed FST values. The results from this

research demonstrates that ancestry labels can be used to approximate genetic similarity, but only in a very simplified way.

CONCLUSION

This project shows that published FST values can be used to build a simple model of genetic distance between individuals based on their heritage. Although the model is highly simplified and uses published data, it provides a way to visualise how ancestry proportions relate to expected genetic similarity. As FST assumes clear population boundaries and only shows overall variation, it simplifies complex ancestry into a simplified number. Overall, this FST analysis provides a quantitative measure of genetic differentiation by the usage of FST, demonstrating how historical and genetic events shape modern lineage and distance across populations.

RESOURCES

Leslie, Stephen, et al. "The Fine-Scale Genetic Structure of the British Population." *Nature*, vol. 519, no. 7543, 1 Mar. 2015, pp. 309–314, www.nature.com/articles/nature14230, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14230>. Accessed 19 April 2026.